

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

GAMIFYING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: MOZABOOK AS A TOOL FOR LANGUAGE SKILLS AND LITERACY DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16995195>

Abstract

The study explores the role of game-like activities in foreign language teaching for Generation Z and Alpha students. It includes a literature review on gamification in language learning and the characteristic features of today's students, as well as a qualitative analysis of mozaBook's features and their impact on language learning. The aim is to present the diverse tools and games offered by the educational presentation software mozaBook, applicable at every stage of a language lesson. The presented activities were implemented with students from Yoan Ekzarh Balgarski Secondary School in Shumen to assess their effectiveness. The research highlights how these digital tools can enhance literacy skills, including reading, writing, and digital literacy, which are essential for learners in the digital age. It also illustrates the effectiveness of integrating game-like activities to improve student engagement and literacy development.

Keywords: gamification; literacy; mozaBook; foreign language teaching; student engagement

Introduction

Nowadays English is considered a global lingua franca and both educators and learners realise its significance as a universal means of communication. However, since "language learning is hard work" (Wright, Betteridge, & Buckby, 2010, p. 2), teachers need to find a way to engage their 21st century students in order to facilitate foreign language acquisition and the development of the four major language skills: reading, listening, speaking and writing. Various aspects of gamification, digitization, and digitalization can be implemented in the English language classroom so that to assist this process and to suit the educational needs of today's students.

Gamification, defined as "the use of game design elements in non-game contexts" (Deterding et al., 2011), is also a pedagogical approach which enables attracting students' attention, improving retention, and fostering active participation. Recent innovations in technology, on the other hand, have led to changes in both the landscape of education and students' attitudes and expectations. The purpose of this article is to examine the role of applying the principles of gamification in foreign language learning and to present some digital-based game-like activities, which can be used to create a dynamic, innovative and interactive language learning environment, thus facilitating language skills and literacy development.

The Role of Gamification in Language Learning

Games are believed to be an innate and engaging way for children to understand their surrounding environment, but their benefits are not limited to young children only. They have found their application in marketing and merchandising because of their ability "to keep users engaged with products and motivated to perform certain behaviors" (Dichev et al., 2015).

Game-like activities are considered a powerful tool in education as well, since they facilitate hands-on learning, creativity, emotional engagement, social interaction, and the development of various skills, thus contributing to students' holistic growth and learning experience.

Scot and Ytreberg (1990), Jill Hadfield (2004), Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2010), Kim, Song, Lockee and Burton (2018) to name a few, have all explored the positive impact that educational games have on students' learning and classroom performance. In the context of teaching English to young language learners, Scot and Ytreberg (1990) discuss games as a means of creating a positive environment, conveying meaning, fostering language interaction, presenting a real challenge and relaxing (1990, pp. 108 - 110). In *Gamification in Learning and Education: Enjoy Learning like Gaming*, the authors suggest the following list of advantages to implementing games and gamified elements in instruction: 1) increase student engagement and motivation; 2) enhance learning performance and academic achievement; 3) improve recall and retention; 4) provide instant feedback on students' progress and activity; 5) catalyze behavioral changes; 6) allow students to check their progress; 7) promote collaboration skills (Kim et al., 2018, p. 5).

In their book *Games for Language Learning*, Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2010) define a game as "an activity which is entertaining and engaging, often challenging, and an activity in which the learners play and usually interact with others". The authors view games as central to language learning and not as a "way of passing the time", since game-like activities can be used to create meaningful context in which the foreign language to be used (2010, p. 2). They discuss the importance of learning styles and classify eight game

types according to the verb summarizing the main activity which language learners are engaged with while playing: 1) care and share (e.g. sharing personal information); 2) do: move, mime, draw, obey (e.g. performing an action based on written or oral instructions); 3) identify: discriminate, guess, speculate (e.g. making guesses and then compare with the facts); 4) describe (e.g. drawing a picture based on someone's description of an object); 5) connect: compare, match, group (e.g. matching images to sentences); 6) order (e.g. put some sentences in order, so that to form a logically connected text); 7) remember (e.g. various memorizing games); 8) create (e.g. writing a poem, etc).

In *Elementary vocabulary games: a collection of vocabulary games and activities for elementary students of English*, Jill Hadfield (2004, p. 4) suggests that "a game is an activity with rules, a goal and an element of fun" and discusses two types of games, namely: *competitive* (participants compete to be the first to reach a particular goal) and *cooperative* (participants work together so that to reach a common goal). Depending on the preferred technique, Hadfield classifies games into several categories: game-like activities based on the information gap principle; guessing games; search games; matching games; matching-up games; exchanging games; exchanging and collecting games; combining activities; arranging games; board games, card games, puzzle-solving activities; role-play activities. (Hadfield, 2004, pp. 4-5).

Kim et al. (2018) view games as having "goals, rules, and interactions" and suggest the following definition: "A game is an action or a set of actions that includes one or more people, objects, or animals, usually in competition with others, that follow a specific set of rules, in order to achieve a goal." (2018, p. 16). They discuss various game genres, such as: board and card games, puzzle games, word and trivia games, racing and sports games, role-playing games, strategy games, etc. and support the idea that any of these can serve as educational games on condition that they meet the educational purposes (Kim et al., 2018, pp. 17-22).

Teaching Digital Natives

Mark McCrindle, an Australian social researcher and demographer, provides a detailed classification of generations, according to which today's students belong to generation Z (born between 1995 and 2009) and generation Alpha (born between 2010 and 2024). There are some differences between the representatives of these two generations in their attitudes towards various aspects. For example, generation Z representatives are more focused on exam results, prefer using touchscreen technology and paying by credit cards, while generation Alpha representatives are more focused on developing learning skills, prefer using voice-recognition technology and making digital payments (McCrindle, 2020). Despite the abovementioned dissimilarities, they share many common features, such as being skillful in using modern technologies since their earliest childhood and being able to apply numerous technological devices in various aspects of their daily lives. These "digital integrators" are highly influenced by the effects of globalization, multiculturalism and advancements in technology, which results in their new attitude to learn-

ing – they expect information and communication technologies to be present and actively used in the classroom.

Digital Tools and Platforms for Gamified Language Learning

Undoubtedly, it is not necessary for educational games to be performed using some form of technology, yet most of today's students tend to perceive information better when it is visualized in the form of images, videos and 3D animations. There are various online educational platforms and software solutions which language teachers can choose from, so that to implement game-based activities in the classroom, thus, engaging their students and meeting learners' expectations. The focus of this paper falls on some of the engaging features of the educational platform mozaWeb (<https://mozaweb.com>) and the educational presentation software mozaBook which can effectively enrich language learning experiences, while promoting active participation and language acquisition. Many educators are also familiar with other web-based tools, such as Wayground (formerly Quizizz) (<https://wayground.com/>), Kahoot! (<https://kahoot.com/>), Quizlet (<https://quizlet.com/>), LearningApps (<https://learningapps.org/>), to mention a few, which allow teachers to create educational content containing various types of game-based activities. These can include multiple-choice quizzes, word grids, crosswords, pair-matching exercises, flashcards, etc. Most such online educational platforms also enable monitoring students' work and tracking their progress.

Implementing mozaBook Game-Like Activities: Enhancing Language Skills and Literacy in the EFL Classroom

The resources of the educational platform mozaWeb and the features of educational presentation software mozaBook (<https://www.mozaweb.com/en/mozabook.php?cmd=download>) can be applied in almost every stage of a foreign language lesson. The platform provides its users with opportunities to create interactive presentations enhanced by inserted interactive content (e.g. 3D scenes, educational videos, etc.) and more than 160 educational tools and games, thus developing various valuable skills, facilitating practicing previously acquired knowledge, enabling experimentation and improving visualization.

Many of these mozaBook tools and games, such as: 'Spelling and grammar', 'Word finder', 'Word cards', 'Lan(g)ame', 'Spelling', 'Letter cards', 'ABC table', etc. are specially designed to develop and enhance the literacy skills of reading and writing. Others, for example 'Test Editor', 'Board games', 'Question sheet', 'Quiz', 'Dice', etc. are more universal and can be customized so that to suit the educational needs of the respective lesson. The rich media library containing various videos and 3D scenes can turn out to be very effective in lessons focusing on content and language integrated learning (CLIL). Moreover, most linguistic games can be set to various languages, thus being useful not only for English language classrooms, but in other classes as well.

The "Spelling" game (Fig. 1) provides young learners with opportunities to practise their spelling by

playing spelling games in one of the following game modes: just learnt (the teacher selects a recently learnt letter and students have to find its position in a word related to a picture), learnt so far (students need to choose letters from the list and find their positions within the word displayed), spelling (students have to

spell the whole word). This tool not only enhances spelling proficiency, but also facilitates the development of fundamental literacy skills, including reading and writing, by reinforcing letter recognition and correct spelling.

Fig. 1 The "Spelling" game

The "Hammer" and the "Image domino" games (Fig. 2) are powerful tools, which facilitate acquiring and practicing vocabulary items by choosing one of three levels of difficulty. Three minutes are allowed for each game, but the countdown option can be turned off if the teacher decides that time limits are not appropriate for their students. The "Hammer" game can be a helpful tool for developing both mathematical and linguistic competence. In its "Word" mode game players need to hammer nails and piles by clicking to certain

depth, so that to complete sentences. In the "Image domino" game players need to logically match the domino tiles in one of the following game modes: images (matching tiles featuring identical images); initials (match two tiles featuring an image and its first letter); words (match tiles featuring an image and the name of the objects). Players need to move the tiles on the board by dragging having in mind that matching tiles rotate automatically.

Fig. 2 The "Hammer" and the "Image domino" games

The "ABC table" tool can be used to generate words with shuffled letters which players need to put in order. Teachers can set which letters have been learnt so far and in what order. They can also create their own games by typing words of their own choice. Words from this tool can also be exported into the built-in Test editor. Such activities promote letter recognition and word formation, enhancing both reading and writing skills through engaging practice.

"Letter cards" is a tool which teachers of young learners can find really useful when teaching the letters of the alphabet. By choosing a letter from the alphabet board, a card featuring an image, printed and handwritten versions of the corresponding letter appears. By clicking on any of the letters, its phonic sound is audi-

ble; by clicking on the image, players can hear the pronunciation of the word (Fig. 3). This interactive approach supports early literacy by reinforcing letter-sound associations and improving phonemic awareness.

The tool "Word cards" offers a collection of more than 2000 words and corresponding example sentences which can be adjusted and filtered based on students' needs. Players can learn about words classes and syllabification. Words, expressions and example sentences can be transferred into the Test editor, thus generating various exercises (Fig. 3). This tool aids in vocabulary building and understanding sentence structure, which are key components of literacy skills in both reading and writing.

Fig. 3 “Letter cards” and “Word cards”

The “Spelling and grammar” tool (Fig. 4) is a card game-like application, which can be used to practise both spelling and grammatical structures at various levels. Teachers can filter and adjust the settings by choos-

ing a grade and a particular category (e.g. spelling mistakes, prefixes and suffixes, comparative and superlative forms, etc.). Students are allowed 15 seconds to answer each question. The current exercise can also be exported into the built-in Test editor.

Fig. 4 The “Spelling and grammar” tool

Tools such as “Code breaker” and “Word finder” (Fig. 5) can be very effective during the introductory stage of a lesson in order to pre-teach or revise some key vocabulary in an engaging way and at a preferred level of difficulty. When using the “Code breaker” tool students need to decode a word or phrase using various symbols, such as bar codes, hieroglyphs, flag signals,

animal footprints, etc. When playing with the “Word finder” tool, students have to find hidden words and expressions in a letter grid. Words are selected by dragging and if the selected word is correct, it turns green. This tool enables teachers to prepare their own word lists accompanied by example sentences, questions or clues, so that to suit their students’ educational needs.

Fig. 5 “Code breaker” and “Word finder”

The “Test” tool (Fig. 6) is a built-in interactive test editor and player which enables teachers to create worksheets containing various types of exercises, such as: multiple choice close (single or multiple selection), true/false, matching, text and gap filling, item ordering,

crosswords, tables, etc. (see fig. 6). Exercises from other mozaBook tools and extras (such as 3D scenes) can also be exported in the Test editor, thus facilitating the process of assessment and receiving instant feedback.

Fig. 6 The built-in “Test” editor and player

The “Board games” tool (Fig. 7) enables teachers to create various competitive games, such as ‘safes’, ‘wheel of fortune’, ‘racing cars’, ‘ball games’, etc. They can either choose from a rich database of ready-made quiz questions by selecting a specific field of knowledge, or customize their own question bank by

Fig. 7 The “Board games” tool

using the “Edit worksheet”. Questions can be multiple choice, gap filling, true/false or containing an oral answer. Teachers can add images, shuffle possible answers and choose the layout of the question. Once created, the worksheet can be applied to all the different “Board games” modes.

The rich “3D scenes” library features rotatable models and animations on various subjects to help visualize the learning content. They can be used as powerful tools in teaching vocabulary, in activating background knowledge, in establishing cross-curricular connections in the English/foreign language classroom and when applying the principles of content and language integrated learning. 3D scenes offer students an exciting learning experience. For example, in the 3D scene “Marie Curie’s laboratory” (Fig. 8), they can observe and even walk around the famous scientist’s la-

boratory, they can learn about her life and achievements, they can watch an animation, play a built-in quiz, etc. Each 3D scene includes an audio recording and a matching script. These resources can serve as a basis for creating listening or reading comprehension tasks. Another useful and time saving functionality is that teachers can generate worksheets in the “Test” editor (thus creating gap-filling, labelling or multiple choice tasks) out of the information in the script. They can also generate games in the “Board games” tool by just clicking on the corresponding button.

Fig. 8 “Marie Curie’s laboratory” 3D scene

Conclusion

The paper is an attempt to illustrate some of the numerous opportunities that foreign language teachers in general, and English language teachers in particular are provided with, due to the current trends in education in the realm of digitization, digitalization and gamification. Living in the digital era requires adapting teaching approaches and learning techniques, so that students graduate from school equipped with the necessary skills and competences.

The benefits of using the digital game-like activities on mozaBook in the English language classroom are undeniable. It can be said that they captivate students' attention, provoke active participation and critical thinking. They enable students to enhance their vocabulary, grammar, literacy, and language skills in an enjoyable and effective way, while being immersed in real-life contexts.

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